

Iron removal from bauxite ores

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Abstract

A process of removing iron from bauxite ore is described. The ore is firstly reduced in CO and H₂ atmosphere to convert iron oxides of bauxite to magnetite or elemental iron. Then material is finely crushed and passed through the magnetic separation. Short characterisation of raw and preheated bauxite is done by using XRD, XRF and EPMA. Additionally, effect of reduction process on total organic carbon was investigated. Experiments shows that once iron phase rendered magnetic it can be removed by magnetic separation. Iron content was reduced by 43% in comparison to untreated bauxite ore with 75% bauxite recovery as non-magnetic fraction.

Introduction

The bauxite is the main Al source for aluminium production. It is a mixture of different aluminium hydroxides in addition with silica and iron oxides as the most important ones. The aluminium hydroxides are removed by leaching with Bayer process and the crystallized aluminium hydroxide is calcined to Al₂O₃ used in aluminium smelters. The Bayer process creates large amounts of bauxite residue (red mud) deposits, where the iron oxides are up to 60% of mass. Red mud is the largest environmental challenge for the aluminium industry. In October 2010, Hungary witnessed a major industrial disaster when the reservoir wall of the Ajka red mud depository failed, spilling 1 million cubic meters of caustic bauxite residue slurry. The collapse led to 10 deaths and over 120 injuries, polluting hectares of agricultural land and the adjacent river system.¹ In 2015, due to the failure of the tailing dam in China's Guangdong Province 2 million cubic meters of red mud slurry was released to the local environment submerging local village.²

The current paper presents the method where iron containing minerals in the bauxite are reduced to magnetite that can be separated from the alumina containing minerals by magnetic separation. The described method can decrease red mud production by iron removal from bauxite before Bayer process thus reduces the environmental problem and cost of waste disposal. The proposed process has also a considerable potential for reducing the cost for chemicals for leaching. Additional magnetic separation methods should be effective in

separating leached solids from leach liquor. Using magnetic separation would provide improved dewatering of leached residue, hence easier disposal of the dewatered residue. Separated iron oxide bearing materials can then be sold as a product instead of being disposed as part of red mud.

Investigations on direct reduction of iron in bauxite are limited in literature. Sadler et al. reported that calcination of refractory-grade bauxite with reducing gas converts present iron to magnetite or elemental iron.³ Removal of organic carbon from bauxite by hydrogen pretreatment was examined by MacDonald et al. They observed that bauxite and its leached residue become partially magnetic after the calcination between 240-400 °C in hydrogen atmosphere.⁴ A recent work on carbothermal upgrading of the Ghana Awaso bauxite reported that it is possible to remove over 90% of the iron oxide content from the bauxite as magnetic fraction.⁵

Material and Methods

Material

The bauxite sample used in the study was provided by one of the Brazilian mining company. Sample was crushed and sieved to particle size between 1-3 mm. A main components and phase composition of the ore are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Chemistry of the sample

	wt%
Fe ₂ O ₃	20.60
SiO ₂	13.40
Al ₂ O ₃	42.40
Gibbsite	54.7
Kaolinite	26.5
Hematite	19.9

X-ray diffraction phase identification of the raw ore showed gibbsite (Al₂O₃·3H₂O) as the major phase, presents with kaolinite (Al₂O₃·2SiO₂·2H₂O) and hematite (Fe₂O₃). Electron Probe Microanalysis (EPMA) images presented on the Figure 1 and Figure 2 show an overview of minerals distribution inside the ore. On Figure 2, all bright areas are Fe/Ti rich phases; most likely hematite and some rutile. They occurred frequently as separate grains with different particle size. Based on visual observation particles can be divided in two groups: the relatively coarse fraction between 50-5 μm and the fine-grained, dispersed in the ore, including particles

smaller than 1 μm . What is worth to mention that samples were very inhomogeneous and differ with phase occurrence from particle to particle.

Figure 1. EPMA mapping image of bauxite showing elements concentration

Figure 2. EPMA image of ore with different magnifications

Total Organic Carbon (TOC) analyse of tested material is presented in Table 2. Bauxite contains low amount of organic carbon around 0.1 wt%, which is still low in comparison to Australian or Jamaican ores where TOC differ between 0.15-0.3 wt%.

Table 2. Total organic carbon in bauxite ore

Sample	1	2	3
TOC [wt%]	0.111	0.11	0.115

Reduction of iron oxide

Two different reactors were used for reduction experiments. A simplified scheme of the experimental setups is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Schematic drawing of the experimental setup: a) DISvaDRI furnace used for direct reduction of oxides (sample mass 100-150 g), b) small scale (40 g) vertical tube furnace

For tests done in DISvaDRI furnace, the reduction of the materials is performed in a crucible as shown in Figure 3a. The gas flow is preheated by flowing down an annulus in the wall of the crucible and enters the charge from below. The furnace temperature is controlled by a thermocouple placed near the heating element, while the other thermocouple controls the temperature in the charge. The crucible is hooked up beneath a balance thus the measurement of the mass loss during experiment was possible. The computer automatically records the time, furnace (controlling) temperature, and sample temperature, weight of crucible and individual gas flow rates to the crucible. Experimental conditions are listed in Table 4. For experiments with CO and H₂, gas was injected when temperature of 500 °C was reached. That was done to avoid carbon deposition at lower temperatures while CO gas was used.⁶

For vertical tube furnace (Figure 3b) reduction gas was injected directly into the crucible through the tube tightly connected to the bottom of the crucible, both made from Alsint. To keep the charge material from falling into the gas carrier tube an alumina plate with holes was placed on the bottom of the crucible. This plate

also provides a more uniform gas distribution inside the crucible. Typically, 40 gram of previously dried sample was heated to target temperature with heating rate 25 °C/min. During the heating the crucible was flushed with the argon gas. Reduction gas was injected when temperature achieved targeted value. After reduction the reactor was purged with argon while sample cooled to room temperature. Target temperatures, holding time, reduction gas and particle size of ore used in this test are given in the Table 3.

Table 3. Experimental conations for experiments done in DisvaDri furnace

No.	Gas	Particle size	Target temp.	Holding time	Weight
I1	CO 1l/min	1-3mm	800 °C	no	100g
I2	H ₂ 1l/min	1-3mm	800 °C	no	100g
I3	Ar 1l/min	1-3mm	800 °C	no	100g
T1	H ₂ 1l/min	3-6mm	600 °C	1h	150g
T2	H ₂ 1l/min	1-3mm	400 °C	3h	150g
T3	H ₂ 1l/min	1-3mm	400 °C	1h	150g
T4	H ₂ 1l/min	1-3mm	350 °C	1h	150g
T5	H ₂ 1l/min	1-3mm	350 °C	3h	150g
T6	H ₂ 1l/min	1-3mm	800 °C	3h	150g

Table 4. Experimental conditions for experiments done in vertical tube furnace

No.	Gas	Particle size	Target temp.	Holding time	Weight
E1	H ₂ 1l/min	1-3mm	500 °C	3 h	40 g
E3	H ₂ 1l/min	1-3mm	350 °C	1 h	40 g
E4	H ₂ 1l/min	1-3mm	800 °C	1 h	40 g
E5	H ₂ 1l/min	3-6mm	600 °C	1 h	40 g

Separation

The Slon separator, wet high intensity magnetic field separation (WHIMS) designed to separate minerals with weak magnetic strength was used. This process combines magnetic field strength and gravity with pulsating flow of material. It is specially designed to operate and separate fine particles, such as hematite, iron-sulphides and silicates.

During the first test, different parameters, like magnetic field, pulsation, size of rod matrix were verified. Magnetic field intensity was controlled by electric current.

Two different rod matrices were used, as depicted in Figure 4. Material used for first run was reduced bauxite ore at 800 °C under CO, with fraction less than 38 µm. After the separation process, samples were dried and analysed with XRF.

Figure 4. Rod matrix applied in SLon test

Based on the result from the initial test the optional parameters were chosen for the next set of the separation experiments where bauxite from different reduction experiments was used.

Results and Discussion

Reduction of iron oxide

All samples of bauxite ore that had been reduced in hydrogen or CO atmosphere at temperature range 350-800 °C became strongly attracted for magnetic field of hand-held low intensity magnet. Colour change of samples from red to grey can indicate that the reduction of magnetite took place during the treatment. However, after the calcination of ore in inert atmosphere at 800 °C neither change in colour nor magnetic properties was observed. Figure 5 presents calcination curves for a bauxite carried out in DISvarDRI furnace at a heating rate of 10 °C/min. Weight loss caused by oxygen loss due to reduction of iron oxide cannot be clearly seen on this figure. Calcination of bauxite in argon atmosphere resulted in highest weight loss, where in this case no reduction reaction should occur. Observed weight loss during the heating was mostly due to the liberation of both unbound and chemically bound moisture from the ore samples, for example Gibbsite dehydrates at 357 °C.³

Figure 5. Typical calcination curve for heated samples under various gas atmospheres

Phases containing iron are very inhomogeneous and appear in different arrangements. Figure 6 shows occurrence of phase containing iron in two different manners. Figure 6a shows most likely ilmenite (white spots) as separate grains spread in Al rich matrix. Figure 6b shows opposite situation where matrix is most likely magnetite (bright phase) with dark Al-oxide matrix.

Figure 6. EPMA picture showing occurrence of iron rich phase in two particles from the same batch (sample reduced in H₂ at 600 °C)

Table 5 presents the TOC in pre-treated bauxite. In all experiments where H₂ was used TOC level in bauxite was decreased down to below detection limit. However, significant increase of TOC was observed for experiment where CO was used as reducing gas. No reasonable explanation was found for this phenomenon, nevertheless hydrogen was chosen to be used as reducing agent for all further experiments.

Table 5. TOC in pre-treated bauxite ores

Test number	Gas atmosphere	Temperature [°C]	TOC [%]
I1	CO	800	0.67
I2	H ₂	800	<0.1
I3	H ₂	500	<0.1

Separation

All separation tests described below were performed on Slon separator. Figure 7 presents experimental conditions for initial test where different parameters were tested.

Figure 7. Experimental conditions during initial test and output from each stage

During the initial test current/magnetic field were decreasing with the following step, as presented in Figure 7. For last two stages, the matrix rods were changed to coarser one. During the last stage, pulsation was used.

In the initial test, 20 gram of sample was used as a feed. After the separation test, 15.09 g was collected as non-magnetic and 3.49 g occurred as magnetic fraction. 1.44 g of sample was lost during the separation or draying process. In other words about 75% of the feed material was recovered as non-magnetic product while 17.5% was recovered as magnetic fraction. The highest non-magnetic output was observed during stage 5, when the low magnetic field, coarse rod matrix and pulsation was applied. Table 6 shows comparison of XRF result of outputs from each stage during the initial separation test with raw bauxite. Sample from stage 4 was not analysed due to small quantity.

Table 6. Comparison of XRF result of outputs from initial separation test with raw bauxite

stage	Non-magnetic				Magnetic	Raw bauxite
	1	2	3	5		
Fe ₂ O ₃ (%)	11.17	11.71	12.23	12.75	33.02	20.60
SiO ₂ (%)	22.70	23.19	23.33	24.01	21.55	13.40
Al ₂ O ₃ (%)	53.62	53.65	52.89	53.59	37.14	42.40

As it can be seen, the iron content was significantly decreased in the non-magnetic fraction for all stages for around 43% in comparison to the iron content in untreated bauxite ore.

Figure 8 shows elemental concentrations in particles from magnetic fraction after the initial Slon separation test. There is still significant amount of Al bearing phase which was not liberated during the crushing process. In addition, Fe phase in particles mostly containing Al-

Figure 8. EPMA mapping image of magnetic fraction after the initial Slon test

Si phase is relatively small, however it was enough for whole particle to be attracted by magnetic field. Further crushing to the lower particle size, either initial feed or magnetic fraction could results in higher efficiency of the separation process.

The next set of separation experiments were planned to run under conditions close to previously described stage 5. Current of 50 A, pulsation and finest rod matrix were used. Reduced materials under conditions listed in table 7 were crushed and sieved to particle size smaller than 37 μm . Sample T3 was split into two batches, and then T3b was run twice for the same conditions in Slon separator to check if repetition of the cycle affects the separation yield.

Table 7. Materials characteristic and separation condition

No.	Gas	Particle size	Target temp	Holding time	Separation in Slon				
					Feed in (g)	Non-magnetic		magnetic	
						(g)	(%)	(g)	(%)
T1	H ₂ 1l/min	3-6mm	600 °C	1h	60	8.3	14	50.9	83
T2	H ₂ 1l/min	1-3mm	400 °C	3h	75	24.7	34	48.5	66
T3a	H ₂ 1l/min	1-3mm	400 °C	1h	35	4.4	13	30.1	87
T3b	H ₂ 1l/min	1-3mm	400 °C	1h	42	4.1	10	35.8	90
T3b-1	Non-mag fraction from T3b				4.1	2.2	54	1.9	46
T4	H ₂ 1l/min	1-3mm	350 °C	1h	70	8.6	12	61.4	88
T5	H ₂ 1l/min	1-3mm	350 °C	3h	70	9.1	13	60.4	87
T6	H ₂ 1l/min	1-3mm	800 °C	3h	30	7.7	28	20.3	72

The non-magnetic fraction is the potential feed for Bayer process. The most preferred situation is to have as high recovery in non-magnetic fraction with low iron content, or the other way around, as low magnetic fraction with high iron content. The highest recovery in non-magnetic product was observed for material T2 (reduced at H₂ for 3h at 400 °C) where 34% was separated as non-magnetic fraction. T3a and T3b which were reduced at similar conditions as T2, but with shorter holding time have lower recovery rate between 10-13%. However, additional separation test for material T3b gave great increase with recovery up to 54%. It seems that not only longer holding time during reduction process but additional loop during the separation process effect with the better recovery as a non-magnetic fraction. Additional reduction time in case of sample T5 (in comparison to T4) did not affect with increase in recovery. Sample T6 where

bauxite was reduced in H₂ for 3h at 800°C has 28% recovery as non-magnetic product. It is relatively high for test presented in Table 7, however it is surprisingly low in comparison to initial separation test where 75% of bauxite reduced in CO for 3h at 800 °C was generated as non-magnetic product. Nevertheless, one must remember that initial test consists of 5 separation stages with diverse parameters. That clearly shows that the huge impact for recovery rate of bauxite ore has separation conditions rather than reduction parameters.

Table 8 shows Al₂O₃ and iron oxide content in magnetic and nonmagnetic fraction. Additionally, iron removal level for non-magnetic fraction is also listed. It describes iron oxide content decreased (%) in comparison to the feed used for separation process.

Table 8. XRF analyse for feed, magnetic and non-magnetic phase after the Slon separation

	Fe ₂ O ₃ (%)	Fe removal level in comparison to the feed	Al ₂ O ₃ (%)
T1	30.0		53.0
T1 mag	31.8		50.8
T1 non-mag	19.2	36%	61.0
T2	14.0		46.5
T2 mag	14.8		45.9
T2 non-mag	12.8	8.5%	47.7
T3	25.7		47.5
T3a mag	27.7		46.5
T3a non-mag	18.4	28.4%	53.6
T3b mag	27.6		46.6
T3b non-mag	21.1	17.9%	51,0
T3b-1 non mag	15.5	39.6%	55.9
T4	26.8		46.3
T4 mag	28.0		45.1
T4 non-mag	19.4	27.6%	51.7
T5	26.2		48.0
T5 mag	27.1		46.2
T5 non-mag	18.6	29.0%	53.4
T6	15.8		55.3
T6 mag	16.8		54.4
T6 non-mag	13.6	13.9%	56.5

Sample T1 (reduced at H₂ for 3h at 600 °C, 3-6 mm particle size) shows the highest iron removal level after the single run in Slon separator. Samples T3a and T3b differ significantly with iron removal level, even if they are taken from the same batch. Additional run with Slon separator increase the removal level up to 39.6% for sample T3b. However, the presented values in Table 8 are still low in comparison to the initial separation test where iron removal level was around 43%. Even for sample T6 where bauxite was reduced for 3h at 800 °C iron removal level was around 14%.

Figure 9. Comparison of recovery as a non-magnetic fraction vs iron removal level. Beside "initial test" all samples were reduced by H₂. Particle size for all samples used during the separation test were less than 37 μm

Since the non-magnetic fraction should be used as feed for Bayer process, combination of the minimum iron content with high recovery as non-magnetic fraction should be the ultimate target. Figure 9 presents bauxite recovery as a non-magnetic fraction and iron removal level for test performed in Slon separator. The highest values gives the initial experiment where bauxite reduced at 800 °C in CO atmosphere was separated through 5 stages cycle. Impact of multiple-pass magnetic separation seems to have significant influence for both iron removal and bauxite recovery, which also can be seen in case of sample T3b1. The influence of reduction conditions parameters on iron removal or bauxite recovery, as non-magnetic product is not evident. It is worth to remember at all reduced samples became very magnetic. Longer holding time in case that bauxite is reduced at 350 °C do not change any of the values. However, in samples heated at 400 °C, longer holding time increases the amount of generated non-magnetic fraction. Reduction

at high temperature also does not indicate better separation output. Material reduced in CO at 800 °C gave the highest separation results, while material reduced in H₂ at 800 °C did not follow this trend. Of course, the influence of reduction gas can play here an important role, however the use of CO gas for reduction of bauxite ore is not practicable due to increase of carbon content. Bauxite reduced at 600 °C at H₂ gave high iron removal level, but quite small fraction was separated as non-magnetic material.

In case that not all magnetic iron is removed from the bauxite before digestion stage, magnetic separation could be used to improved post-digestion stages in Bayer process. First of all, magnetic separation can be used for separating the leached solid from the liquor but also it can be used for dewatering of leach residue.

In order to check that the bauxite residue remains rendered magnetically susceptible after the leaching process 24.3 g of magnetic fraction from sample T2 was leached at 143 °C with 189 ml of 2.5M NaOH. Digestion time was 70 minutes. The leaching test was performed by Hydro Alumina Quality Support laboratory. As it was examined by hand-held low intensity magnet the residue was still strongly magnetic.

Conclusions

Pre-treatment of bauxite with reducing gas, both CO and H₂ at temperatures ranging from 350 °C to 800 °C was investigated. Iron impurities in bauxite were rendered magnetically susceptible for all temperatures when reduction gas was applied, presumably by forming magnetite.

Reduction in H₂ gave decrease total organic carbon level, while the usage of CO increased carbon content in bauxite. Thus, the H₂ is preferable reducing agent for reduction of iron oxides in bauxite.

Iron phase occurs frequently as separate grains with different particle size. Based on visual observation particles can be divided in two groups: the relatively coarse fraction between 50-5 μm and the fine-grained, dispersed in the ore, including particles smaller than 1 μm.

Once iron phase rendered magnetic, these iron phases can be removed by magnetic separation. Wet high intensity magnetic field separation showed to be suitable method for removal of iron phase from bauxite ore. Iron content was

reduced by 43% in comparison to untreated bauxite ore with 75 % bauxite recovery as non-magnetic fraction.

Extent of iron removal is more affected by conditions used during the magnetic separation than the conditions used during the reduction process. Thus, more work should be done to determine most effective separation settings.

Pre-treatment of bauxite with hydrogen made the bauxite leached residue magnetic. That gives opportunity to use magnetic separation for separation leached solid from leach liquor or to improve dewatering of leached residue.

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